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Maximizing the Potentials of Yoruba Folklore for Moral Development among Youths in Ede, Osun State

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Abstract

The current vices and displays of immoralities by youths in Ede, Osun State, contradict Yoruba culture. This calls attention to folklore, a vital aspect of Yoruba culture which was used in the pre-colonial Yoruba society to successfully socialize youths positively. This study therefore examined Yoruba folklore and its implications for moral development among the youths of Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. The study is built on functional-performance theory, a combination of functionalism and performance theories calling attention to societal functions of folklore and its communicative tendencies. The population was constituted by staff and students of Adeleke University and Federal Polytechnic and the custodians of culture, in Ede. Cluster sampling technique was used to divide the population into three sub-groups while simple random sampling technique was used to choose 5 lecturers, 5 culture custodians and 20 students as participants. The in-depth (IDI) and Key Informant (KII) interview guides were used as the instruments for this study. The study established that various folklore genres are still recognised in Ede, each with

its unique values. It was also established that folklore is gradually fading out as a youth moral development tool. The study ascertained that the integration of folklore and social media is necessary for the restoration of folklore and for youths' easy access. It concluded that both old and current methods should be synchronized to give folklore a new facelift. Therefore, it was recommended that folklore should be incorporated at every level of education, integrated into social media and communicated via Yoruba language.

Keywords: Folklore, *Omoluabi*, Moral Development, Yorùbá, Youth, Ede, Osun State

Introduction

Immorality of all kinds is pervasive and on the rise among Nigerian youths today. Corruption, gambling, betting, yahoo, yahoo plus, cheating, indulging in money rituals, gangsterism, drug addiction and abuse, sexual immoralities, indecent dressing such as sagging among males, and body-revealing clothing by females are examples of immoral behaviour (Akanbi, 2014). A Yorùbá saying states that *iwa rere l'eso eniyan* (good character is the beauty of the mortal). This demonstrates that anything adverse to the exhibition of decent behaviour in society has departed from the moral standard and hence is inappropriate. As a result, several vices and immoral behavior by youths are considered abhorrent in Yorùbá culture. This draws attention to folklore, an important component of Yorùbá culture that was employed in pre-colonial Yorùbá society to positively socialise youths.

In Yorùbá culture, an individual's moral character earns him a prestigious place in society, so he is referred to as *Omoluabi*— a concept that emphasizes good character; it is a metric for intelligence, accomplishment, and beauty. These traits of *omoluabi* are inherent in Yorùbá folklore. They are equally used as a yardstick for good character. As Yorùbá, youths are supposed to apply the principle of *omoluabi* in whatever they do. The exhibition of *omoluabi* qualities by youths also indicates that such individual has received good family instruction and is of exemplary worth in society, hence the proverb: "Charity begins at home". Unfortunately, the 21st Century acts of Nigerian youths utterly contradict the ideals of *omoluabi*, which have been supplanted by foreign qualities and values.

Yorùbá use folklore to explore relevant themes and difficulties in their lives. It supports cultural ideals and resonates to both young and old people in general. The Yorùbá's lifestyle reflects their wisdom, knowledge,

understanding, instruction, and life experiences as they change over time. Folklore, in all its forms, provides universal ideals important for rectifying moral aberrations. They are veritable instruments for moral training for children, youths, and adults.

Despite these invaluable traits, folklore is rapidly losing popularity and relevance (Akanbi, 2014). This is linked to the new Western political, social, moral and legal principles established during the colonial era, which became ingrained in the cultural system through civilization and spread throughout the social, cultural, and religious systems (Nsereka, 2019). However, the Western values and culture embraced by Nigerian youths contradict African indigenous folklore. As a result, it is critical to highlight the efficacy of adopting folklore genres to combat deviant behaviours among the teeming immoral young people and to prevent morality in society.

The use of folklore for the moral development of Nigerian youths is no longer popular, resulting in moral degradation among those who are expected to be tomorrow's leaders. Folklore instilled strong morals in the pre-colonial Yorùbá population, fostering youth development. However, the entrance of Western culture and social media into African communities has negatively altered the standard and resulted in a quick shift in social norms. Behaviours that were once considered unacceptable in traditional Nigerian society are now allowed and even applauded. Today, Nigerian youths, particularly those in Ede, are confused as a result of contradicting signals from parents and elders on the one hand, and the mass and social media on the other. Today's youths use social media to seek advice, unlike the Yorùbá traditional society that relied solely on folklore and the family institution.

There is a need to revisit the Yoruba archives to discover what worked in the past: folklore and all its genres (Igba, 2016, 245-251). An exploration of the existing literature on folklore revealed that different researchers have worked on folktales as a tool for moral development in young people both within and outside of Nigeria (Sesan, 2014; Azubuike, 2013; Taiwo, 2014). Few of these investigated how folklore could be utilized to instil values in young people and to recognize societal norms (Igba et al, 2019, Ojukwu & Esimone, 2015). Other research focused on folk music, a component of folklore, to reaffirm its value (Jamolovna, 2021; Ibekwe, & E. Ojukwu, 2020, Akande, 2023). While these studies have underlined the importance and values associated with folklore, the factors that have contributed to its

deterioration and diminishing importance among youths, as well as its possibly integration into social media have been overlooked. Since these previous studies have not done enough in recognising the factors that have contributed to the deterioration and diminishing importance of folklore among youths, as well as its possibly integration into social media, this current study is designed to address this gap.

Clarification of Concepts

Moral Development

Moral development has to do with the emergence, change, and understanding of morality from infancy through adulthood (Satianingsih, et al), including the youthful age. In other words, it is a progressive procedure that spans through lifetime in various ways and is influenced by an individual's exposure and attitude when confronted with moral concerns involving varying eras of physical and cognitive development. It equally refers to a specific code of conduct that is derived from one's culture, religion, or personal philosophy that guides one's actions, behaviours, and thoughts. This further establishes the fact that folklore and moral development are interrelated since moral development is derived from one's culture (Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020).

Folklore

Literally, folklore has a double meaning ((Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020). Hence, on one side, it is defined as traditional knowledge of the common people and as such, represents a body of material: stories, songs, beliefs. Likewise, it is a separate science closely linked with literature and history (Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020).

Youth

There appears to be no uniform definition of youth. Africa, the Global South, and many other countries have long asserted that youth is defined by culturally defined social processes that mark the transition from childhood to adulthood, rather than a range of years. The United Nations defines youth as a phase of transition from childhood reliance to adulthood's independence and recognition of our interdependence as members of a community. In other words, youth is a more flexible category than a definite age group” (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). The African Youth Charter defines youth

as “any individual between 15-35 years of age and seeks to resolve longstanding debates about defining youth within the African context and based on Africa’s development realities” (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). According to Nigeria's 2019 National Youth Policy (NYP), a youth is defined as person aged 15-29 (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). For this study, the NYP's (2019) youth classification is used.

Theoretical Framework

Functional-Performance Theory

This is a combination of functionalism and performance theories. According to Akporherhe & Oghenerioborue (2021) functionalism is developed by Bronislaw Malinowski (1884-1942). The theory, according to the two scholars, centres on the utilitarian functions of oral materials produced in traditional society including legends, folksongs, proverbs, riddles, folktales, myths and festivals, to mention a few. The performance theory also known as ethnography of communication, on the other hand, was proposed by Dell Hymes initially in his paper: *The Ethnography of Speaking* (Ray et al., 2011). The theory considered the interactive forms of communication, describing its role “as a cultural system” (Igba et al. 2019). Building this study on the two theories is thereby justified since functional theory vividly brings out the functional values inherent in folklore while the performance theory explains the variety of contexts in which it is communicated within a given society.

Methodology

The exploratory research design is adopted for this study. The population of this study consisted of all the staff and students of the selected departments (History, Library Science, Mass Communication and English) in Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State. The population also included all the staff and students of Library and Information Science of Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State. The students were chosen because the bulk of them were young people who fell within 15-29 years age range, the age range accepted for youth classification by 2019 National Youth Policy in Nigeria and because they were students their intellectual capacity and direct connection with the subject at hand were extremely valuable to this study. The population also included lecturers from the two tertiary institutions earlier mentioned. They were used because their fields of study

were connected to the problem under inquiry. Custodians of culture viz: elderly chiefs, community leaders and family leaders in Ede who were well-versed in the traditions of Yorùbá and Ede, in particular, were consulted. Ede was chosen because of its richness in Yorùbá culture (Nolte, and Ogen, Olukoya, 2017).

The population was divided into three (3) sub-groups using the cluster random sampling technique: students from the two tertiary institutions under study, lecturers and elders who were cultural custodians in Ede. A purposive random sampling technique was then used to select twenty (20) students (ten/10 from each school) who had lived in Ede for at least five (5) years, as well as five (5) lecturers who were experts in fields related to the study: four from Adeleke University and one from Federal Polytechnic (because Adeleke University offers four courses related to the study, whereas Federal Polytechnic only offers one, i.e. Library Science). Still using sampling technique, five (5) custodians of the town's culture were chosen from the third sub-group. Overall, thirty respondents were chosen for interview. The in-depth interview and key informant interview guides were utilised to collect data for this study. The researcher and her assistants met with each respondent individually. These data were organized thematically and contextually analysed.

Data Presentation

Suitable Folklore Genre for Moral Development among Youths

The first objective of this study is to ensure that folklore is appropriate for moral development among youths in Ede. Most respondents recognised that folklore genres include folktales, myths, legends, and fables, folk music/songs, talking drum, proverbs, tying and dying, carving, pottery, folk dance, folk poems such as panegyrics/praising poetry, folk rhymes, bride's lamentation, dirge, and so on. Each of these sorts of folklore has a specific function and purpose. Overall, respondents saw these folkloric genres as methods for connecting youths to their ancestral past, preserving culture, and, most importantly, teaching, instilling, and boosting morality, particularly among young people. Folkloric genres are employed during festive occasions and in diverse communication contexts. Both young and old participants opined that folk story is the best type of folklore that is most suitable for youth moral development. One of the participants mentioned:

Oriki/praise poetry and fables are some of the Yorùbá folklore types. Fables, due to their didactic nature, teach morals. Oriki/Praise Poetry/panegyrics strengthen marital relationship and boosts morals. Also, oriki tells you who you are, what your ancestors have done and how you can improve on it. To me, the fable, a sub-type of folk story, is the best because it brings out morals. (KII, FP Lecturer, 2023)

In corroboration with the above response on the suitability of folklore for moral development, a participant has this to say:

Folktales, legends, statues, folk music, and myth are some of the folklore types in Yorùbá culture. To me, myth is the best because it centres on past heroes' stories of success and failure, which can guide youths to tread cautiously. Myth makes you remember who you are, and who your ancestors are. (IDI, FP, 2023)

In addition, a custodian of culture emphasized:

Moonlight tales, proverbs, riddles, chants, oriki/praise poetry are the popular Yorùbá folkloric genres. Folk stories connect youths to their historical backgrounds; riddles, myths and folktales deepen youths' understanding of their culture. The nighttime when the moon is out is the time chosen to expose children and youths to these oral traditions. All of them are useful but folktale is the best since it has the capacity to teach youths their ancestral history, which invariably teaches them morals. (KII, Culture Custodian (CC), Religious Leader, 2023)

In support of folktales as the best form of folklore, another community elder noted that:

Drumming, folk songs, folktales, myths and legends are types of folklore. Generally, folklore is used to strengthen youths and teach them morals. However, folktale is the best because it strengthens youths, develops their listening skills and imparts deep wisdom in them. (KII, Community Elder, 2023)

Another community leader also strongly supported the fact that folktale is the best. He said:

Ekun iyawo popularly called the bride's lamentation, *ijala*, *ere ode* (hunters' chant), *iyere ifa*, moonlight tales, *alo apamo* (riddles), folktales, legends, myths are some of the folklore genres in Yorùbá culture. They are usually taught. Picking the best is a difficult task

but I'll like to go with folktales because it is rich, very rich. It combines history with morals and virtues. If children are exposed to it, it will make them to become somebody in life. (KII, Religious Leader, 2023)

Proverb too was identified as one of the folklore components that can be used for moral development. This fact is supported thus:

Proverb is just the best. Whenever, I misbehave, my mother will scold me and tell me *omo ti a ko to lo ngbe ile ti a ko ta*. Each time I hear that, I come back to my senses. (IDI, AU, Male, 2023)

Apart from folktales, folk songs/music and proverbs, talking drum is also regarded as one of the components of folklore that significantly shapes moral development among the youth. A Federal Polytechnic student gave reasons that:

Drumming, proverbs, and monuments are some of the folklore types in Yorùbáland. But the most important is the talking drum. To me, talking drum is the best as it gives youths the opportunity to be meaningfully engaged and exhibit their talents. (IDI, FP, Female, 2023)

However, all the various components of the folklore were identified as good and useful as one of the participants mentioned. Myth, legend, orilki/praise poetry and folktales are parts of Yorùbá folklore, but none can be said to be better than others since each of them has its own purpose and focus. (KII, Adeleke University Lecturer, Male, 2023)

Finally, the importance of language in conveying the moral lessons embedded in any components of folklore cannot be underestimated. Language in this case, is important. One of the community elders interviewed laid an emphasis on this in his words that:

Folklore genres include folktales, riddles and legends. They are generally used to intimate youths with the past and teach them moral lessons. However, we cannot pick the best from folklore genres that are not presented via Yorùbá language. (KII, CC, Community Elder, Female, 2023)

Significantly, the importance of language in teaching morals through folklore needs to be adopted in this present age and communication.

Factors Influencing the Ineffectiveness of Folklore

According to available literature, the internet, social media, and other technological instruments have decreased the impact of folklore among Nigerian youths. These technology platforms just distance the youth from traditional and folklore genres, which were formerly used to transmit moral precepts. The second research question of this study seeks to determine the efficient use of folklore as a tool for youth moral development. One of the participants identified foreign culture as one of the reasons why folklore is ineffective among today's youth. He maintained that:

Folklore is no longer fashionable because of the adoption of foreign culture. (KII, Adeleke University, Lecturer, 2023)

To another participant who is a community leader, folklore as a means of moral development and a way to transport moral lessons has really dwindled. The participant emphasised the need of indigenous language to bring back the effectiveness of folklore as noted:

Folklore can only be effective if native language is used, or else, the result will be an English-oriented folklore. (KII, Community Leader, Female, 2023)

Perhaps Yorùbá folklore has lost its relevance as a result of the ubiquity and pressure of English-speaking among youths. While English has become a priority, the Yorùbá language, which is used to deliver most of these cultural elements, has died away because most youths cannot speak or comprehend it. Because it is difficult to hear and/or speak Yorùbá, it will be incredibly difficult to grasp when utilised to communicate moral lessons through storytelling. Yet, emphasising the link between mother tongue and folklore, Mzimela (2016), opines that mother tongue is often used to sustain and convey cultural beliefs. A student, who shares a similar opinion on the importance of language, stated:

Folklore has lost its effectiveness as a tool for youth moral development because of the non-inclusion of Yorùbá as a subject by some schools. (IDI, Female, 2023)

A community/religious leader confirms that the ineffectiveness of folklore among youth is due to western pollution from foreign culture, which has become the new means of transmitting moral messages and teachings. He explained this:

Folklore has lost its effectiveness as a result of importation of foreign culture through its “might is right” weapon. The might is

right syndrome came and silenced the voice of truth in our culture. Hence, someone described western civilization as western contamination. The point is our own tradition detested dishonesty but when the European legal system was introduced, crimes began to increase since the court of law must try criminals before convicting them. Since then, the law and law enforcement agents have become very powerful. Whatever the law or its enforcer says is the final, whether right or wrong. That has really silenced our morally-inclined culture. (KII, Community/Religious Leader, Male, 2023)

Meanwhile, while advocating for an immediate remedy due to the disappearance of folklore, a lecturer voiced great concern that folklore could be completely lost if proper precautions are not taken. A lecturer-participant therefore said:

We are at a critical bend; we are at verge of losing our folklore in Yorùbá society. If something is not done urgently, there will be problem. (KII, Lecturer Participant, Male, 2023)

Colonialism and the entrance of foreign religions have had a negative impact on Yorùbá youths' usage of folklore. Folklore and other cultural components have dwindled but have not totally lost their significance in imparting vital moral lessons and values in the society. This is explained as follows:

Folklore has not totally lost its effectiveness as a weapon for youth moral development in Ede North Local Government Area. It is only gradually dying because it is suffering from neglect/abandonment because of the negative impact of colonialism and foreign religion which created the impression that our culture is evil. The truth of the matter is that the Yorùbá society is an evolving one. Our culture has its negative and positive sides. All we need to do is to take the good aspects and discard the negative ones. (KII, Lecturer Participant, Male, 2023)

While it is agreed that folklore and its genres have not been effective over time, it is imperative to know that some people still make folklore relevant. These are those that have lived with and benefitted from the elders. These categories of people have such advantage to demonstrate this cultural identity wherever they go and thus, retain the effectiveness of folklore. A community leader stated that:

Folklore has not absolutely lost its effectiveness because people do not easily forget their culture and norms. Moreover, an adage says: *Bo ti wu korun ko mu to, sanman dudu die yoo wa* (Every cloud has a silver lining). This adage implies that every sad, difficult or hopeless situation has a comforting or more hopeful aspect. Superficially, it seems folklore has lost its effectiveness, but looking at it critically, this is not totally true for as people (especially, *awon omo odo agba*, those nurtured by culturally-inclined elders), travel round the globe and interact with others, they spread their norms and traditions. Drama also assists in retaining the effectiveness of folklore. (KII, Community Leader, Male, 2023)

Since the Yorùbá language is still taught in schools, the values of folklore remain important. The teaching of Yorùbá language and the presence of some artifacts, statues of heroes and heroines in Yorùbáland convey volumes, according to a student:

I believe that folklore has not totally lost its effectiveness because Yorùbá is still taught in schools and there are statues all around speaking volumes about folklore. As the young folks move around in their communities seeing these statues everyday, there is an awareness of their tradition. (IDI, Adeleke University, Ede, Female, 2023)

According to another student of Adeleke University, the quality of time of youths plays a significant role in the usage of folklore. Most times, the youths listen to foreign music and watch foreign videos, which only propagate foreign culture. Meanwhile to gather them to listen to cultural Yorùbá music and watch Yorùbá films to learn our culture is always a problem. The participant noted:

Folklore is gradually going into extinction because the listening span of youths is very short so tying them down to receive cultural values via oral tradition is quite difficult. (IDI, Adeleke University, Female, 2023)

Still supporting same opinion, another student respondent has this to say:

Folklore is not as popular as before because modernization has offered better ways of teaching moral lessons. For instance, youths can access several films on the television, VCD or even on their android or Hi-phones at their own leisure. (IDI, Adeleke University, Female, 2023)

Integrating Social Media and Folklore for Moral Development

One strategy to make Yoruba folklore relevant again in imparting moral values is to employ the most appealing medium to youths, namely social media platforms. Thus, the notion of combining folklore and social media to educate values and morals to Ede North LG young people in Osun state is not out of order. Hence, a participant stated:

Omo ina la nran sina (to get a wildfire, you need to send a lesser fire on errand). Since youths are in love with social media, it is a brilliant idea to use social media platforms as channels to teach them moral values since nowadays, the youths' relationship with social media is like that of Romeo and Juliet. Social media platforms focusing on folklore can be created but activities there should be placed under restrictions by the government. Parents and stake holders should guide in this respect to avoid abuse. (KII, Community Leader, Male, 2023)

Another respondent in the Local Government says:

It goes beyond social media. Children should be exposed to digital or language programming from cradle like the Indians do. My major exposure to folklore was through Indian films. (KII, Federal Polytechnic Lecturer, Male, 2023)

Another interviewee on integration of the folklore with social media said:

Social media can be created to teach the upcoming generation. They can even make money out of it like Adejoke Ewa Ede, Lekan King Kong and so on. These people are recently chanting lineage poems, dancing in the traditional ways, using talking drum and teaching both foreigners and indigenes what they know and do. These platforms can also be used to store and show folktales that will convey moral lessons for our youths (KII, Community/Religious Leader, Male, 2023)

As suggested by a participant:

Culture custodians can come together to create a social media platform for teaching and popularizing folklore. (IDI, AU, Female, 2023)

A youth respondent in the community under study said:

Social media platform where folk music can be showcased can be created. For instance, we have '*Afin Ilu*', created by Adewale Laoye. (IDI, FP, Male, 2023)

Discussion

The study found that folklore genres used for various communication situations are effective instruments for youth moral development. Folklore genres, including folktales, fables, proverbs, and *oriki*, are widely regarded as cultural instruments for moral development. They are methods by which youths in society are required to demonstrate the concept of *omoluabi*, which defines a 'cultured and well-mannered social being'. Folklore and its genre, based on cultural transmission theory, describe how cultural values, beliefs, and norms are passed down from generation to generation in a society, shaping individuals' behaviours for the sake of the society's sustainability. Folklore became a framework for guiding youths in internalising rules and values that satisfy society standards.

While most participants acknowledged the relative nature of folklore genres, they emphasised that each serves a distinct cultural and moral function, underscoring the value of an integrative folkloric approach. Similarly, functionalism theory recognises the importance of each cultural aspect in maintaining societal balance. Riddles, for example, promote critical thinking; *Ekun Iyawo* (bride's lamentation) fosters empathy and anticipation on marital duties; and the talking drum promotes creativity, communal cohesion, and subtle communication. This represents a concept of moral development as multifarious emotional, cognitive, and behavioural, with different folklore genres addressing these elements differently yet complementarily.

Walters believes that the essential values embedded in folklore should be used to ethically train today's youths, as the same technique worked for our forefathers (Walters 2007: 275-284). Stebbins, corroborating this, stated that folklore can be used to impart decency, moral virtue, and ideals in children (Stebbins, 2001). Yorùbá folklore informs Yorùbás about their societal structure, essential values, taboos, and sanctions (Odeh, 2022: 1-27). Furthermore, Efua regarded folklore as the most functional component of the traditional verbal art, through which the people's ideas, morality, and social attitudes are conveyed from one generation to another (Efua, 1976). However, she (She is a female Ghanaian playwright) also stated that this

functional tool has been virtually forbidden by educational policy and is regarded with contempt in educational institutions (Efua, 1976). Meanwhile, it is necessary to pay attention to fulfil cultural transmission theory that folklore is a means for passing on moral ideals and expected behaviours among adolescents, which include respect for elders in society, dignity, love, and appropriate behaviour whether one is watching or not. Cultural imperialism is one major factor that influences folklore as an instrument for youth moral development due to the dominance of foreign studies and media, foreign religion, colonisation, and the neglect of indigenous language due to westernisation. Due to all these factors, local cultural practices and values have been eroded and folklore has lost its savor as a youth moral development tool. There is nothing like moonlight tales (*alo agbagbe* and *alo apamo*), proverbs, etc., as they have all been replaced by European tales carved under Hollywood and films. This also shows that that folklore is not included in the education and entertainment arenas. That is why Barigbon blamed this in-effectiveness of folklore on Western invasion through civilization and Christianity (Nsereka, 2019). One participant's description of Western civilization as "Western contamination" reflects the postcolonial critique of cultural hegemony, where indigenous African cultures have been delegitimised and branded as primitive or evil. Still, the data presents a nuanced optimism rooted in cultural resilience theory. Though folklore faces challenges from modernisation, and postcolonial westernisation, it has not been totally eroded. Community elders, lecturers, and some youths that have gained from traditional upbringing continue to propagate folklore and embody its values. The adage '*bo ti wu korun ko mu to, sanmo dudu die yoo wa*' metaphorically signifies hope and cultural persistence. Therefore, to retain and sharpen folklore as an instrument of morality, it is necessary that writers should inculcate folklore in their writings and artists and musicians should also include it in their plays and music respectively as suggested by Akínyemí and Ajíbájé (Akínyemí, & O. Ajíbájé, 2016). Oni agreed that writers are indebted to the oral traditions because of the rural environment in which they grew up (Oni, 2001). For instance, Akínwùmí Ìsòlá studied Yorùbá genres of incantations and many other oral traditions. Adeleke confirmed that Ìsòlá's exposure as a child at Lábòdé village via Ìbàdàn is the foundation of his *Ogun Ọmòdé* (Adéléké, 2016). Kólá Òní also has an oral tradition background due to

environmental and parental factor (Akínyemí, & O. Ajíbájé, 2016). This goes a long way to retain the core values of folklore and avoid distortion.

The participants equally suggested a creation of physical and virtual libraries under a strict supervision of morally upright and culturally inclined adults. Others prescribed the inscription of folklore genres on marbles, while learning of programming languages and codes that will enable a child to write programmes, design websites and create robot or artificial intelligence were also suggested. Some respondents are of the view that just like the Indians, if the younger generation are well nurtured in Yoruba folklore, it will aid cultural promotion. In respect to the use of multimedia to promote various aspects of folklore, it was suggested that developing Yoruba folktale animation will assist in training youths to develop virtuous qualities and have socio-cultural awareness thereby preserving our cultural values (Alade et al, 2015: 113-120). In addition, it helps in reviving, sustaining and popularising Yorùbá folktale among present and future generations.

Lastly, the study explored the synergy between folklore and social media, with all participants upholding its potential for promoting moral values among youths. For instance, Lekan Olaleye (Lekan King Kong) and Ajoke Ewa Ede, use digital platforms to showcase Yoruba culture. Adeoba and James noted that Olaleye's Instagram content demonstrates social media's function in circulating cultural genres (Adeoba & James, 2025: 260-277). *Afin Ilu*, a cultural centre in Ede created by Prince Adewale Laoye, uses Facebook and the Talking Drum to celebrate Yoruba heritage and this has been recognised globally (Zulu, 2015): 90-95). It was agreed by the participants that effective use of social media could foster cultural rebirth. In supporting this, a scholar noted the importance of integrating culture and local wisdom into digital spaces, with Alade noting that the internet offers crucial support for folklore's survival (Zulfitri, & S. A. Teguh, 2021: 01-17). Also, suggestions were made for accommodating more indigenous platforms like the Nairaland (Ahmed, 2023, 24), echoing China's strategy of promoting local culture through home-grown media (Ahmed, 2023, 24), while AFIDFF in Abuja also records African folktales online, aiding cultural preservation and youth empowerment (Ahmed, 2023, 24). This has been proven to have very positive results, as well as boost youths' economy, in agreement with an interviewee's submission.

Conclusion

This study concludes that folklore is a powerful tool for youth moral development, especially within the Yoruba cultural context. Through folktales, panegyrics, proverbs, and other oral traditions, youths can learn societal values, norms, mores, and heroic ideals. Folklore not only corrects deviant behaviour, but also instils into individuals moral character, cultural awareness, and listening skills. Despite challenges like westernisation, colonisation, and religious influence that have led to the neglect of indigenous languages, folklore still retains its relevance through drama, school curricula, community art, and partly, social media. The message is that if strategically revitalised and integrated into modern platforms and education, folklore can bridge generational moral gaps. Scholars and cultural practitioners affirm that the survival and promotion of folklore are essential for nurturing morally upright, culturally grounded youths prepared to lead responsibly.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. To revitalise folklore as a potent tool for youth moral development, it is imperative to reintegrate it into Nigeria's formal education curriculum at all levels.
2. This reintegration should go beyond mere language instructions, it should include structured lessons on folktales, proverbs, panegyrics, and other oral traditions that emphasise societal norms and moral values.
3. Specifically, all these attributes of folklore should be made compulsory in all the indigenous languages in Nigeria: Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa.
4. Schools should create spaces for storytelling sessions, drama, and cultural competitions that display the true context of the tradition and allow students to interact directly with these traditions.
5. Teachers should be equipped with the cultural and pedagogical skills necessary to teach folklore effectively.
6. In addition, writers, dramatists, musicians, and artists should be encouraged through grants, fellowships, and institutional support to incorporate folklore into their creative works. This magnanimous act from the government and grant bodies will serve as incentives for more people to promote indigenous folklore. This fusion of creativity and

tradition can modernise and preserve oral culture, while instilling ethical consciousness in youths. Literary figures with deep-rooted exposure to oral traditions, such as Akínwùmí Ìṣòlá and Kọ́lá Òní, exemplify the importance of grounding creative expression in indigenous cultural heritage to retain the integrity and didactic function of folklore.

7. Furthermore, there is an urgent need to develop both physical and digital infrastructures for the preservation and dissemination of folklore. Cultural institutions should establish folklore libraries, museums, and digital archives, supervised by morally upright and culturally literate individuals.
8. In today's digital era, youths should be empowered with programming and media production skills to enable them to build websites, animations, games, and applications inspired by folklore. This approach blends tradition with innovation and opens economic opportunities for youth.
9. More importantly, the use of social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok should be strategically used for our advantage by circulating folklore content in engaging formats. Examples such as Lekan Olaleye, Ajoke Ewa Ede, and cultural initiatives like Afin Ilu demonstrate that folklore can thrive in digital spaces.
10. Government and private stakeholders should therefore support the development of indigenous social media platforms that promote local content, like China's model, thereby securing the moral and cultural education of Nigerian youths while fostering a broader cultural rebirth.

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